

FEM Study on the Interface Crack in Layered Composite Material

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Abstract

A versatile numerical scheme is formed to solve the finite interface crack problem in three spatial dimensions. This scheme consists of special crack-tip elements and contact elements to be used in a displacement based FEM. The asymptotically exact solutions are incorporated into crack-tip elements with hybrid variational principles and thus the intrinsic difficulties, such as singularity and mixed mode, are accurately treated. Utilizing this numerical scheme, the stress intensity factor and contact area are determined for a penny-shaped interface crack problem in $[45/-45]_T$ Graphite-Epoxy laminate.

Keywords: Three-dimensional interface crack, Hybrid FEM, Contact

1 Introduction

In the last decade or so, interest in the elastic interface crack problem has re-emerged due to the fact that interface cracking, sometimes also called delamination, is one of the most commonly encountered types of damage in the failure of composites. During this period, significant progress has been made in the fundamental understanding of interface cracks in general anisotropic materials [1], [2], [3].

Ting [1] obtained an explicit asymptotic solution near the crack-tip area where crack surfaces are open and thus traction-free. Much of the previous work was reviewed by, for example, Gao [2] who also expressed the solution in a compact form using the complex potential representation. The open crack-tip field exhibits three different singularity modes, e.g, a classical square-root singularity and two additional complex conjugate singularities. These complex valued singularities produce oscillatory stress fields and crack face interpenetration. To overcome these unrealistic phenomena, Comninou [4, 5] replaced an open (traction-free)

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crack surface boundary condition with a closed boundary condition. Recently, Gao [3] extended Comninou's model for isotropic interface cracks to a contact model for a more general anisotropic interface crack. This extended contact model removes the oscillation behavior at the crack-tip for arbitrary anisotropic interface cracks.

Although significant progress has been made in asymptotic analysis of the interface crack, no versatile method to treat three-dimensional finite interface crack problems in general anisotropic material has been obtained to the author's knowledge. The lack of general solution method is due to the involved complexities of the crack surface contact nonlinearity and coupling between all three fracture modes. This paper introduces the first numerical scheme to the stated problem. This scheme consists of special crack-tip elements, a contact element and an iteration algorithm. The crack-tip elements are developed separately for open and closed crack-tip fields. The open crack-tip element represents the asymptotic field of an interface crack with the open crack surface condition [2], while the closed crack-tip element represents the asymptotic field of an interface crack with the closed crack surface condition [3]. The formulation for both crack-tip elements is based on the hybrid stress model in [6].

The developed numerical scheme is applied to solve a penny-shaped interface crack in $[45/-45]_T$ Graphite-Epoxy laminate. The key results of the present study are the shape of contact zone and the stress intensity factors. The contact zone shape is complicated and, the open and closed crack-tip field change in a 60° period along the circular crack front. The obtained stress intensity factors follow the definitions in [2] and [3] for open and closed cracks, respectively.

2 Numerical Scheme

2.1 3D crack-tip element

For three-dimensional interface crack problems, the complete expansion of the exact solution in the vicinity of a curved crack front is not readily available. This prevents the use of the mixed hybrid method in [7]. If it is postulated that plane strain exists in the vicinity of the curved crack front as in [8], then an available solution is the singular term of the asymptotic solution for plane strain problem. Using the singular term, either the hybrid stress or hybrid displacement method can be used to formulate a special crack-tip element. The present study utilizes the hybrid stress method.

Consider a three-dimensional body containing an interface crack with arbitrarily shaped crack fronts. The body is discretized into small elements for a FEM calculation. The detailed elements along the crack front are given in Figure [1], where the crack front of arbitrary shape is represented by piecewise straight-line segments. Four brick elements (basic elements) fully surround the crack front and share the crack front. These basic elements can be classified as type A or A' element for those that contain the crack surface, and type B or B' element for those that do not contain the crack surface. The assemblage of these four basic elements forms the crack-tip element. Note that the crack surfaces are either open or

Figure 1: 3D crack-tip element geometry.

Figure 2: 3D twenty-node crack-tip element.

closed depending on the type of crack-tip elements. Figure [2] shows a twenty-node crack-tip element which is made by assembling of four eight-node basic elements. The node numbering is presented in this figure. This twenty-node element is further specified according to the incorporated eigensolutions. The “OCT3D20 element” contains an open interface crack-tip field while the “CCT3D20 element” simulates a closed interface crack-tip field.

The element stiffness matrix of the crack-tip element is derived from the modified complementary energy functional Π_{mC} with two independent field variables, the equilibrating stress σ_{ij} and boundary displacement \tilde{u}_i , namely

$$\Pi_{mC}(\sigma_{ij}, \tilde{u}_i) = \sum_{n=1}^4 \left[\int_{V_n} \frac{1}{2} S_{ijkl} \sigma_{ij} \sigma_{kl} dV - \int_{\partial V_n} T_i \tilde{u}_i dS \right] \quad (1)$$

where stress σ_{ij} satisfies the equilibrium equation, S_{ijkl} is the elastic compliance tensor, T_i is the surface traction obtained from the stress σ_{ij} , \tilde{u}_i is the boundary displacement.

In a crack-tip element, the assumed stress includes the asymptotic solution term and

the regular polynomial term, namely

$$\sigma_{ij} = (\sigma_{ij})_s + (\sigma_{ij})_r \quad (2)$$

where the first term corresponds to the singular solution which can be obtained from the complex potential functions (in [2] for an open crack and in [3] for a closed crack) and the second term contains only regular polynomials. The subscripts s and r refer to the singular and regular terms, respectively. $(\sigma_{ij})_r$ is selected to satisfy the equilibrium equation and stress-free conditions over the crack surfaces. As a result, the total assumed stress, σ_{ij} , satisfies the equilibrium and crack surface conditions, i.e., traction-free conditions for the open crack or closure conditions for the closed crack. The closure conditions can be completed by constraining the boundary displacements of lower and upper crack surfaces to move together in the normal direction. Following procedures in [6], an element stiffness matrix of the crack-tip element can be obtained. This stiffness matrix can be assembled with those of regular isoparametric elements to produce a global stiffness matrix. A detail derivation can be referred to [9].

2.2 Contact element and iteration algorithm

The contact problem is nonlinear since the area of contact is not known prior to the application of loads. A finite element treatment of the contact problem is penalty method and iteration [10]. Unlike regular elements, the crack-tip element cannot be applied in a straightforward fashion to the contact problem because of the unknown crack surface boundary condition near the crack front. To overcome this difficulty, a pre-analysis problem is set up. The pre-analysis is a problem having all the crack surfaces in contact. The crack surface condition near the crack-tip can be predicted by the sign of the contact normal stress in the pre-analysis problem. An open crack face condition is expected where the normal stress is positive, while a closed crack face is expected where the normal stress is the negative. Based on the sign of the normal stress, proper type and size of the crack-tip element can be selected for the iterative solution procedure by the Newton-Raphson method. Once the iteration converges and the contact solution is obtained, the initial choice of the crack-tip element size should be verified. If necessary, both the type and size of the crack-tip element are adjusted and the iteration performed again. The iteration algorithm can be summarized in the following steps:

1. Run the pre-analysis problem.
2. Determine the type and size of the crack-tip element.
3. Perform the iterative solution method (Newton-Raphson method).
4. Check the set up of crack-tip elements.
5. If necessary, adjust the set up of the crack-tip element and go back to step 3.

Figure 3: Penny-shaped crack in a cube.

3 Penny-shaped crack under shear loading

Figure [3] shows a cube of dimension $2L \times 2L \times 2L$ containing a penny-shaped crack of radius $a = L/10$. The global Cartesian coordinates (X, Y, Z) and cylindrical coordinates (r, θ, Z) are drawn in the same figure. The Y direction is normal to the crack surface. With reference to this coordinate system, the crack occupies the region $Y = 0, 0 \leq r \leq a$. Material #1 occupies $y \geq 0$ and material #2 occupies $y \leq 0$. Due to the unknown crack face condition, the full body is modeled without considering possible symmetry or antisymmetry of loading and geometry. The finite element mesh consists of twenty four planes of nodes at 15° intervals about the Y -axis. Figure [4] shows a detailed picture of the element lay-out in the upper portion of a constant θ plane. The OCT3D20 or CCT3D20 elements surround the circular crack front zone of $0.85a \leq r \leq 1.15a$. This finite element model consists of 1930 nodes, 5790 degrees of freedom from 24 twenty-node crack-tip elements and 1872 isoparametric six-node pentahedron and eight-node hexahedron elements.

The considered material is Graphite-Epoxy laminate with fiber directions misorientated by an angle 90° . The elastic stiffness matrix of the Graphite-Epoxy in [11] is used. Material #1 is rotated by 45° and material #2 is rotated by -45° around the Y -axis ($[45/-45]_T$ Graphite-Epoxy laminate). The oscillation index (ϵ) is varying periodically along the crack front with a period of 90° [2]. Since the present crack-tip elements incorporate a crack-tip field based on a piecewise constant stress intensity factor within a 15° subdivision, only three discrete ϵ 's are used to evaluate the asymptotic crack-tip field for the crack-tip elements along the crack front.

The shear loading ($\sigma_{yx} = 1$) is applied at the outer boundary. From the isotropic study [9], a large crack face contact is expected, which can be checked by the pre-analysis problem. The sign of the normal stress, within the crack-tip elements, of the pre-analysis

Figure 4: Detailed mesh lay-out of constant θ plane in the FEM model of the penny-shaped crack.

problem suggests the following conditions along the crack front.

$$\text{closed} = \begin{cases} 0^\circ \leq \theta \leq 60^\circ \\ 120^\circ \leq \theta \leq 180^\circ \\ 240^\circ \leq \theta \leq 300^\circ \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

$$\text{open} = \begin{cases} 60^\circ \leq \theta \leq 120^\circ \\ 180^\circ \leq \theta \leq 240^\circ \\ 300^\circ \leq \theta \leq 360^\circ \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

This shows that the crack-tip field changes in a period of 60° . The proper twelve CCT3D20 and twelve OCT3D20 elements are placed along the crack front according to equations (3,4), respectively.

With this set-up of crack-tip elements and an iteration criteria of 10^{-8} , three iterations yield a converged solution to this problem. The calculated contact area, as shown in Figure [5], represents the XZ plane projection of the gap between the upper and lower crack surfaces. Based on the calculation, it is found that the major contact zone is in area of $Z < 0$ and also include small fraction of the area $Z > 0$. This contact area is quite different from and more complicated than that of an isotropic bi-material in [9]. If one postulates that the energy dissipation (e.g. by friction) along the closed portions of the crack front is substantially larger than along the open portions, then the complicated contact zone morphology for anisotropic interface cracks suggests more irregular crack growth and more complex delamination configurations. The resulting interfacial stress intensity factors are shown in Figure [6]. The stress intensity factors for open crack front are evaluated at 0.0001 from the crack-tips ($\hat{r} = 0.0001$). K_{II} and K_{III} produce undulating values along the circular crack front. The non-zero opening mode (K_I) is presented along the open crack front.

This work can be summarized as followings: First, a versatile numerical scheme for

Figure 5: XZ plane projection of the penny-shaped crack surface gap in the $[45/-45]_T$ composite laminate under shear loading (σ_{yx}).

Figure 6: Stress intensity factor (k) along the penny-shaped crack front in the $[45/-45]_T$ composite laminate under shear loading (σ_{yx}).

treating three-dimensional interface crack problems was developed. Second, using the developed scheme, a penny-shaped crack in $[45/-45]_T$ Graphite-Epoxy laminate under shear loading was solved. Stress intensity factor and contact zone geometry were obtained.

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